

Alberto Tadiello CORALE

Endlesssssong

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CORALE. Endlesssssong: Damping as a Sonic Refuge

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Damping could be read as a defensive gesture, but it also operates as an act of care. It involves creating a distance (whether material or affective) so that impact does not arrive as a fracture but as something softened and partially absorbed. To protect, though, is not necessarily to refuse contact but to hold it differently: to let force pass through layers that dilute it and return it transformed.

In *CORALE. Endlesssssong*, Alberto Tadiello unfolds the idea of damping as more than an acoustic procedure: it becomes a way of building a sonic refuge for the whales and humans who inhabit the piece. The sounds that compose the work never appear in their raw state; the artist subjects them to successive acts of recording and re-recording. Each migration from one device to another accumulates traces of interference and ambient residue. Rather than preserving the purity of the signal, this process allows the sound to become increasingly contaminated and opaque. What takes shape is no longer a transparent transmission, but a dense, amniotic field of resonance, something that holds its distance and yet continues to vibrate on a parallel frequency. In this context, noise and pollution are not treated as intrusions but as essential materials. They weave an acoustic patina that softens edges and dissolves hierarchies between foreground and background. The resulting texture echoes what Anna Tsing calls “contaminated diversity”: a form of collaborative adaptation that emerges within human-disturbed ecologies. Following this logic, Tadiello gathers the urban hum of Buenos Aires and intertwines it with whale vocalizations, not to erase their friction but to let them unfold within a more spacious and protected temporality. In this suspended field, languages and voices-human or otherwise-shift toward a condition that is less linguistic and more bioacoustic: a mode of communication grounded in resonance and interdependence, where meaning does not vanish but expands beyond the rational and extractive logics of human thought.

This perspective resonates with a broader ecological and ethical question: what does it mean to listen without extracting meaning? As suggested by the Institute for Post-natural Studies,² the task is no longer to decode the whale's vocalizations but to create space for its language. This aligns with the work of theorists like Tim Ingold,³ who reflects on an “education of attention”, a form of perceptive attunement to the environment that acknowledges the interconnectedness of all life forms. Ingold emphasizes that listening should move beyond mere information extraction and instead foster relationships based on empathy and respect. In this light, refuge is redefined not as an escape from harm, but as a site where communication must be relearned, where attention becomes an ethical practice, a way of being present and receptive to other forms of life and their needs. Through this lens, *CORALE. Endlesssssong* enacts damping

as a way of creating an acoustic refuge: a gesture of empathy that softens the violence of transmission so that fragile signals might endure. It proposes a poetics of attenuation as ecological attention, understanding a refuge not as a retreat from the world but a re-scaling of how the world reaches us. To dampen here is to make listening possible again; not as decoding, but as coexistence; not as retreat, but as an opening to the multiple voices that compose our shared constellations of life.

¹ Anna Tsing, “Contaminated Diversity in ‘Slow Disturbance’: Potential Collaborators for a Livable Earth,” in *Why Do We Value Diversity? Biocultural Diversity in a Global Context*, edited by Gary Martin, Diana Mincyte, and Ursula Münster, RCC Perspectives 2012, no. 9, 95–97.

² Institute for Postnatural Studies, “The Whale Refuge Cartography,” in *Moby Dick. The Whale. The Story of a Myth from Ancient to Contemporary Art*, edited by Ilaria Bonaccossa, Marina Avia Estrada, and Michela Murialdo, 215–231. Genoa: Allemandi, 2025.

³ Tim Ingold, *Being Alive: Essays on Movement, Knowledge and Description*. London: Routledge, 2011.

CORALE. Endlesssssong

Alberto Tadiello

CORALE. Endlesssssong is an eight-track audio composition born from the interweaving of human songs and the songs of various species of cetaceans. The work developed during a residency period in Buenos Aires and a journey through the Valdés Peninsula area in the province of Chubut, Patagonia. The sequence of tracks blends laments, funeral dirges, human speech-like utterances and babbling with vocal units, calls, phrasings, themes and songs of humpback whales, dolphins, orcas and, above all, southern right whales, cetaceans that migrate along the coasts of the Argentine ocean. The fusion of these sounds was further mixed with a great many recordings made in the city of Buenos Aires, whose acoustic landscape was an important sensory experience. All the tracks were conceived together, growing as a single super-organism, where the concept of “crown shyness,” a particular phenomenon of plant growth, became both a generative matrix and a metaphor. The so-called “crown shyness”, which shows plants of the same species growing together in a limited space without touching, is a kind of natural geopolitical paradigm: one of respect and protection for a space of personal growth, an ethic of free coexistence.

Under the sign of this proximity and relational quality, the tracks were conceived as a single corpus: an album, a sound film, a set of impressions and modulations that draw near to and brush against one another, always taking up again the timbres and temperatures just closed in the preceding track. Each segment, in turn, is generated from the dust and residue left by the previous modulation, opening onto further developments. The final section, which in a reprise references the opening of the composition by returning to the initial atmospheres, makes explicit a kind of folding and circular development, revealing an endless progression, an internal loop.

The subtitle itself is an onomatopoeic play that stretches the final “S” of “endless” and the initial “S” of “song” into a long hiss, repeating it the number of times which, when overturned, becomes the algebraic symbol for infinity. The audio materials used were gathered omnivorously from different sources: amateur videos, documentaries, podcasts, online platforms and archives, recordings made personally or found via apps, and documents that were suggested or sent to me. The entire digital editing process required that the files be regularly moved from one device to another through physical recordings, without using Bluetooth transfers or downloads.

Every time a file had to be used, it was first re-recorded from one device to another. In this capture process, all the noises of a neighbouring soundscape entered as well: a layer of pollution and acoustic dirt which, through its accumulation, gave the composition a muffled, amniotic, almost dense or underwater timbre. A background which, like a patina of

depth or a filter, created an amalgam of noise, an increase in the thickness of the modulations. Many of these transfers between recording devices were carried out in various bathrooms, places par excellence distinguished by their hard coverings, mirrors and glass that increase reverberations and refractions, as well as by concave forms that naturally emphasize echoes and singular acoustics.

In all the tracks, the vocalizations of southern right whales always appear, like low-frequency pulsations that, in different variants, become obsessive and vaguely hypnotic mantras. Some of the calls used are “ghost” voices: samples made in the 1970s that remained archived in the databases of foundations, research centres and museums, and which obviously belong to individuals unlikely still to be alive. Long sequences of powerful exhalations were also used in the composition. The geysers that whales emit in order to breathe resemble violent jets of air produced in hollow tubes, and they resound like blasts from pneumatic horns. Also, extremely important and highly evocative was the impact of the Patagonian wind, which disturbs and saturates the frequencies in every attempt at recording. Many samples come from the city: from the white noise of air conditioners to bus compressors, from traffic to emergency sirens, from the mewling of fighting cats to birdsong. By contrast, the choice of human melodies used was very precise: in particular, a ritual chant from Salento, a funeral lament from Abruzzo, and a mountain lullaby from Veneto. These materials were deformed as if through stretching, until they reached the typical timbre of a magnetic tape player struggling wearily and moving forward with difficulty, recalling the sound of a radio immersed underwater, of a walkman with dying batteries, sinking, losing strength and submerging. Tears and other audio segments were borrowed from jazz, post-punk, post-rock, drone music, ambient techno and dark ambient tracks, all freely elaborated and shaped, often insistently superimposed.

This narrative, this album, opens under the effect of an almost bewitched enchantment, with the slowed-down voice of an elderly woman performing the Salento moroloja. The lament remains in the background, entangled with long feline moans and deep whale pulsations. The sounds fold in together and become increasingly distant and intense, swelling the famous Abruzzese “Mara Maje” with inexorable slowness and depth. In the third movement, a vague yodel makes explicit all the emptiness between the peaks and spires of a submerged world, recorded with the windows open during a torrential downpour. The song loses any verbal reference or connection to a decipherable language; the human presence becomes ever less identifiable, and the external disturbance becomes more persistent and incisive. The chorus approaches a biophony, an animal phonology. For a moment it becomes pure vulnerability, verging on emotion: an incessant call for help, an imploration, a moment of poignant solitude and disorientation. As the audio proceeds, it slowly ripples and roughens: belows, grunts, roars, burps, grimaces, chaos, countless puffs and cries launched by fleeing birds arrive, overlapping with the thunder of an oceanic wind close to a wartime bombardment, filling and blinding every possible frequency.

A packed melee of sounds twists together, strikes against itself and erases itself, without respite. The penultimate movement slowly calms the tumult and opens vast desert spaces, populated by distant surviving calls and faint guttural blows. Everything seems wrapped in a great emptiness and in an impending feeling of ending. The outro is a clot of ghost voices that points toward a new spell.

Corale. Endlesssssong: the care of listening

Andrea Mattiello
FESTAS. Festival of Art and Science

Life vibrates. Natural processes and animal communications can be understood as sound vibrations. Animal species communicate through distinguishable sound vibrations. In *Homo sapiens*, these vibrations became structured into phonemes, becoming words and reasoning: that *logos* which has governed the agency and presence of our species on Earth from the earliest cave pictograms to recent artificial intelligence. *Sapiens* then became so effective at communicating that, from remote times, it developed sophisticated forms of sound expression which, beginning with sounds alone, passing through voices with words and singing with sounds, then returned to sounds alone, including through musical instruments; and which, as with other animal species, cetaceans for example, make it possible to articulate complex messages.

Corale. Endlesssssong by Alberto Tadiello is a sound work articulated in eight tracks and conceived as a 46'18" loop. Born from a residency in Buenos Aires and a subsequent journey to the Valdés Peninsula in Patagonia, it gathers the sounds of humpback whales, dolphins, belugas, orcas, and southern right whales, presenting them together with human lamentations, dirges, utterances, and babbling, as well as with sound materials from the urban landscape of Buenos Aires. A continuous and relational sonic matter emerges, in which the human, the animal, and the environment tell their stories without any break in continuity. In *Corale*, our voices, words, songs, and stories are added to those of animals and environments, pointing to the idea that other species tell their stories with their own sounds, even though we are not yet fully able to decipher them. From the emerged surface of the Earth to the aquatic submerged world, Tadiello's work chorally gathers, in particular, the narratives suggested by funeral songs and by the sounds of different cetacean species, thus evoking a story of effective environmental conservation.

The whale sounds interwoven in *Corale* recall our relationship with them, presenting them as subjects of global responsibility. After millennia of extermination, since the 1970s coordinated global actions based on science, along

with programs such as *Save the Whales*, have reduced the risk of extinction for these ocean mammals, leading to the international moratorium on commercial whaling and to the increase in the humpback whale population: animals that are fundamental to the processing of carbon on the planet. Scientific research into climate phenomena shows that, although exposed to serious environmental threats, whales remain essential agents in the absorption of atmospheric carbon through the oceanic biological pump. In this story, the song of humpback whales has played a fundamental role in conveying conservation and protection projects internationally.

In *Corale*, the song of cetaceans also acquires a significance that goes beyond biological data and opens onto an anthropological and political reading. In 1977, whale sounds were included by NASA on the two Golden Records carried by the Voyager 1 and 2 probes, together with images, music, anthropic and natural sounds chosen to represent the diversity of terrestrial life and culture. At the very moment when humanity was sending the song of humpback whales into space as a sign of life on Earth, those same whales were at risk of extinction.

This tension between destruction and guardianship returns in *Corale*, where cetacean song, poetically taken up by Tadiello, like the song engraved on the Golden Records destined for the cosmos, ceases to be a naturalistic curiosity and becomes an emblematic element of what the Earth tells about itself: a universal element that exceeds the human species, recognizing the more-than-human not as a resource but as a constitutive part of a shared destiny. Harmonizing our song with that of cetaceans becomes testimony to our capacity to design a future in which nature and culture are integrated within a horizon of shared prosperity.

This proposition brings together the arts, scientific data, and environmental civic engagement, making *Corale* a work that reflects the themes and intentions of a project such as *FESTAS. Festival of Art and Science*, part of the project *The HuT - The Human-Tech Nexus*, funded under Horizon Europe. Its first edition is structured around the theme “NEXUS” as a space for dialogue and connection among artistic practices, scientific reflection, and public participation. The festival seeks to explore the role of art in communicating complex and socially urgent scientific issues, addressing the vulnerability of territories and communities in the face of extreme events, while promoting a form of awareness that exceeds the limits of traditional technical-scientific dissemination.

By connecting nature, science, and culture, *Corale* experientially shows how the natural is intertwined with the artificial, the technical, and the symbolic, and how the human cannot be thought except within a network of relations with other forms of life. The work renders nature audible as relational complexity, transforming listening into a space of thought. In this way, an ecological ethics is generated, in which the world is inhabited not as a space of domination and exploitation, but as a system of relationships of symbolic and political care.

In its circular movement, in the controlled fusion of species and soundscapes, and in its capacity to hold proximity and difference in tension, *Corale. Endlesssssong* demonstrates how art constitutes a form of knowledge production that is not alternative to science but complementary to it, converting information into experience and awareness into perception. The “endless song” evoked by the title is acoustic continuity and the persistence of an uninterrupted relationship among living beings, environments, and imagination. The reference to Voyager is therefore evocative: whale song, having become a message entrusted to deep space, testifies that non-human sounds are instruments with which to imagine the future. This song, originating in the ocean depths, stretches toward infinity along the cosmic trajectory of the Voyagers, a ray that navigates from our planet toward the infinite without end—endless, precisely. Finally, *Corale* recounts the centrality of the action of care that originates in initiatives such as *FESTAS*, with public dialogues among scientists, artists, and citizens. This curatorship is crucial for promoting forms of analytical listening directed toward nature and human societies. In *De Rerum Natura* (III, 933-9), Lucretius imagines nature asking us: «What is so dear to you, mortal, that you indulge excessively in grief, and weep and lament death? For if the life you have lived until now has been pleasing to you, and if all joys, as though gathered in a cracked urn, have not flowed away, nor perished once they had become unpleasant, why do you not withdraw like a guest sated with life, and with a serene heart, foolish one, take secure rest?» From a teleological perspective, the questions addressed to humanity reveal the senselessness of those who, fleeing death, consume nature as a source of experiences, and invite us to a life free from fear through listening and through the care of nature by means of measure and quiet. Like Lucretius, *Corale* promotes knowledge and a shared, measured use of the planet, beginning from poetic contemplation, in the sense of *ποίησις, poiesis*: that creative making from ancient Greek which generates through words and through listening to them. In this sense, Tadiello invites us to listening as a creative act, the condition by which we are fundamentally human only within nature, and by which nature is such only with us within it. Without the species that live in it and name it, nature remains a sum of cosmic forces. The sound traces, anthropic and non-anthropic, on the golden records of the Voyager probes and in *Corale*, are our cosmic choral song, telling the lifeless universe the stories of everything that is living, and how these stories are necessary for there to be nature.

A note by the Foundation

Francesca Blandino
Fondazione Morra Greco

Aligned with the vision of the EDI Global Forum project-platform, the Fondazione Morra Greco, a contemporary art center active for twenty years, understands the museum not as a static space but as a living, multidisciplinary organism, rooted in its surroundings and capable of constant transformation. Its participation at *FESTAS*, part of the Horizon research project *The HuT - The Human-Tech Nexus*, fits into this trajectory, strengthening the dialogue between our Education Department and the hybrid universe that connects contemporary art and science.

In this context, the Foundation welcomes *CORALE. Endlesssssong* (2024), Alberto Tadiello's sound installation, which transforms the museum space into an active resonating chamber, where sound becomes a material for investigation: a work that invites the public to engage with vibration and frequency, moving beyond traditional visual experience.

Through this experience, the Foundation confirms its role as a laboratory of citizenship, where the multidisciplinary interweaving of science and art becomes the engine of new practices of engagement, mediation, and hospitality. In this place, where keywords are encounter, discovery, openness, and continuous transformation, we demonstrate how the cross-pollination of knowledge is the most effective tool for inhabiting the present and imagining the future of the extended museum.

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